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Guidelines for the Appraisal of ESS Data for Long-Term Preservation and Archiving

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Executive summary

Securing the long-term preservation of relevant data is an essential component of sustainable data culture and responsible research data management within Earth System Sciences (ESS) and science in general. ESS relies heavily on the availability of temporal-spatial data about the current and past state of the Earth. Consequently, a vast amount of data is being collected and produced in various processing levels and variations, not all of which has a lasting value beyond the original framework it was created for. Thus, it is essential to have clear appraisal processes and frameworks in place for assessing, filtering, and selecting the data of lasting value that has to be preserved in the long term.

This document provides guidance and suggestions on how an approach to appraisal of ESS data could be designed. On the one hand, these guidelines intend to illustrate the importance of appraisal as a critical aspect within research data management as well as raise awareness to existing appraisal practices and their potential applicability for research data. On the other hand, these guidelines aim to outline core appraisal criteria for ESS as well as offer suggestions for a cooperative approach to appraisal processes and frameworks in ESS. Given the relevance of appraisal throughout the data life cycle, the target group of these guidelines are data producers, infrastructure providers for long-term preservation, and stakeholders shaping the overall data culture in ESS alike.

Abbreviations

DCC – Digital Curation Centre

DFG – German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft)

DIN – German Institute for Standardization (Deutsches Institut für Normung)

DMP – Data Management Plan

EOSC – European Open Science Cloud

ESA – European Space Agency

ESS – Earth System Sciences

FAIR – FAIR Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation

GeolDG – Geological Data Act (Geologiedatengesetz)

GOME – Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment

ISO – International Organization for Standardization

M2.4 – NFDI4Earth Measure 2.4 Data in Long-Term Storage

NFDI – National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur)

NFDI4Earth – NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences (NFDI Konsortium Erdsystemforschung)

RDM – Research Data Management

TDR – Trustworthy Digital Repository

WDCC – World Data Center for Climate

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1 Introduction

A key component in moving towards a sustainable data culture in Earth System Sciences (ESS) and science in general, is to secure the preservation of relevant research data in the long term. While in many scientific disciplines a retention timeframe for research data of ten years¹ has been established, digital long-term preservation aims at ensuring the authenticity, integrity, access, and interpretability of data throughout technological and cultural changes over time, potentially indefinitely. In the NFDI4Earth measure M2.4 “Data in Long-Term Storage” we develop and provide materials and guidelines for the improvement of long-term preservation of ESS data, aiming to facilitate an easy to understand entry point to relevant aspects on this topic.

ESS relies heavily on the availability of temporal-spatial data about the current and past state of the Earth. This data serves as the basis for understanding processes, cycles, interactions, or changes within the Earth’s sub-systems, such as e.g., the atmosphere, hydrosphere, or geosphere, as well as the Earth’s system as a whole. Consequently, in ESS a vast amount of data is being collected and produced, ranging from raw unprocessed instrument data, data and data products of various processing levels, derived or accumulated data, to modeling and simulation data output. While most of this data serves a specific purpose or research question, not all of it has a lasting value beyond the original framework it was created for.

Thus, it is essential to have procedures and frameworks in place to assess, filter, and select the data that has to be preserved in the long term, potentially indefinitely. This critical function within archival practices is called appraisal. At its core, appraisal is the process of evaluating and determining the lasting value (also referred to as archival value or continuing value²) of data in a structured and systematic way. This serves as a basis for an informed, transparent, consistent, and accountable decision-making process which data should be preserved in the long term.

While appraisal is a well-established practice within the archival community, there are no defined standards for the appraisal of research data for long-term preservation. The results of our survey on long-term preservation in ESS³ as well as our workshop on appraisal criteria in ESS⁴ both indicate uncertainty as well as the need for supporting material and guidance within the community on this topic. The goal of these “Guidelines for the Appraisal of ESS Data for Long-Term Preservation and Archiving” is therefore to provide guidance and suggestions

¹ In accordance with the “Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice” from the DFG, see: (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2022)

² (The National Archives, 2022)

³ (Paul-Stüve, Schürmann, & Valena, 2024)

⁴ (zu Castell, et al., 2024)

on how an approach to appraisal of ESS data could be designed. On the one hand, these guidelines intend to illustrate the importance of appraisal as a critical aspect within research data management (RDM) as well as raise awareness to existing appraisal practices and their potential applicability for research data. On the other hand, these guidelines aim to outline core appraisal criteria for ESS as well as offer suggestions for a cooperative approach to appraisal processes in ESS. Given the relevance of appraisal throughout the data life cycle, the target group of these guidelines are data producers, infrastructure providers for long-term preservation, and stakeholders shaping the overall data culture in ESS alike.

Considering the diverse sub-disciplines within ESS and their specific requirements as well as the diverse data types and data output in ESS, these guidelines can only offer abstract guidance and serve as an entry point on this topic as well as hopefully provide an impulse for further more detailed discipline and/or data type specific guidelines and recommendations.

2 Why Appraisal matters

Given the exponential growth of data produced by contemporary research in ESS, not all data can or should be preserved indefinitely. This chapter provides an overview of the reasons why the appraisal of research data is essential for a sustainable data culture and should be given attention within RDM.

2.1 Preventing Information Overload

Research projects and missions in ESS produce a vast amount of data in various processing levels, ranging from raw data with little to no documentation, temporary working data, to well-documented processed and/or analyzed data and data products. While most of the data might be essential during the active phase of a research project, it does not necessarily retain a lasting value beyond that context. Preserving all data indiscriminately contributes to an information overload, making it difficult for future users to identify, interpret, and reuse valuable datasets.⁵ Appraisal aims to distinguish relevant, meaningful data from data that no longer serves any useful purpose, ensuring that the preserved data is coherent, sufficiently documented, and aligns with the overall needs, requirements, and objectives of the scientific community.

From a user perspective, appraisal also supports trust in preserved data collections. Researchers are more likely to engage with curated collections when they can be confident that only relevant, meaningful, and qualitative data has been deliberately selected according to clearly defined criteria. Thus, appraisal contributes not only to a more efficient preservation effort, but also to the credibility and impact of preserved research data.

2.2 Preventing Redundancies in Preservation Practices

Redundancy is another challenge that appraisal seeks to address. The same research data may exist in multiple versions, formats, or locations, including personal storage devices, institutional systems, collaborative platforms, or (subject-specific) repositories. Uncoordinated or unnecessary duplicate preservation of the same data can lead to confusion, decreased findability and usability, wasted resources, and inconsistencies over time.

Appraisal aims to identify and determine which version of a dataset should be considered authoritative and thus preserved in the long term. Furthermore, the appraisal process aims to detect whether the research data has already been adequately preserved elsewhere, e.g., in a trustworthy digital repository (TDR), making it unnecessary to allocate resources to duplicate preservation efforts. For appraisal processes and long-term preservation efforts in general, it is

⁵ (Whyte & Wilson, 2010)

recommended to have clearly assigned responsibilities and stewardship roles for research data during the active phase of a research project as well as a designated curation institution (e.g., a TDR) for the subsequent long-term preservation of the selected data, helping to reduce the risk of redundant and duplicate preservation. This contributes to more coordinated and efficient preservation efforts and preservation ecosystem, both within research projects and institutions as well as for the scientific community as a whole.

2.3 Cost and Resource Considerations

While cost considerations in theory should not play a role in the appraisal process of determining the lasting value of research data, it is nevertheless a crucial argument why appraisal should be a critical function within RDM. The decision to preserve digital research data, potentially indefinitely, always comes with a short-term and long-term cost.

The Short-term cost of long-term preservation of digital research data mainly centres around the preparation of the data in order to be able to be preserved in the long term in a designated curation institution (e.g., TDR). This involves creating and compiling sufficient documentation and metadata for the data to be independently understandable, migration to a sustainable file format (if required), as well as the clarification of legal and ethical aspects, requiring the allocation of time and human resources.⁶

The long-term cost arises from ongoing curation and active preservation within a designated curation institution. Digital long-term preservation is an ongoing commitment rather than a one-time action. It requires monitoring of cultural and technological changes and undertaking preservation actions (e.g., migration to newer file formats) as needed in order to maintain meaningful access to the content of the preserved data in the long term. These long-term costs arise from ensuring the maintenance and update of the complex storage and preservation infrastructure and systems as well as the availability of sufficient expertise.⁷

Appraisal ensures to focus the limited resources available for preservation efforts on critical research data that have been deemed to be of lasting value. Preventing an unchecked accumulation and overload of unnecessary, low-value, or redundant data contributes to a more sustainable and efficient data culture as well as targeted resource allocation within individual research institutions and facilities as well as the scientific landscape as a whole.

⁶ For more detail on how to prepare research data for long-term preservation, see the NFDI4Earth Guidelines for the Preparation of Data for Archiving: (Valena & Schürmann, 2024)

⁷ For more details on digital long-term preservation within a designated curation institution (e.g., TDR) see the NFDI4Earth Guidelines for repository providers - Improving long-term preservation of digital research data: (Schürmann & Valena, 2026)

3 Appraisal Practices in the Archival Community

Appraisal is an established and central function within modern archival practices with a long history of developing theoretical and methodological concepts and frameworks on how to conduct an appraisal process. Central to these developments was the growing awareness that appraisal decisions not only shape the understanding of the past and the collective memory of a society but also form the basis for future research and knowledge production. An essential contribution to appraisal theory was made by the American archivist Theodore R. Schellenberg in the mid-20th century, who introduced a distinction between different types of value, allowing for more structured, systematic, and standardized appraisal processes and decisions.⁸ While originally developed for the appraisal of records from governmental, administrative, and organizational entities, these conceptual frameworks remain highly relevant in today's appraisal practices also for other kind of data and information. Several ongoing projects are currently working on the evaluation of their applicability for research data as well as the development of specific standards for the appraisal of research data. Among these are on a National level the nestor working group "Prozesse und Kriterien zur Bewertung von Forschungsdaten"⁹ [Processes and criteria for the appraisal of research data] and on a European level the project "EOSC EDEN Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level"¹⁰.

This chapter will highlight some of the essential conceptual frameworks and approaches on appraisal as well as contextualize their relevance for possible appraisal practices for research data.

3.1 Primary and Secondary Value

A first distinction is made between the primary and secondary value of data. The primary value refers to the data's usefulness to their creator for the original purpose it was created for. In the case of research data, its primary value is mostly closely linked to the original research project or mission, e.g., data that is being collected or created to answer specific research questions, validate findings, and support scientific publications.

The secondary value relates to the potential lasting value for others than the original creator and beyond the original purpose that the data was originally created for. In science, this can

⁸ (Schellenberg, 1996 (first published in 1956))

⁹ https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/DE/Arbeitsgruppen/AG_Archivstandard/ag_archivstandard_node.html (accessed: 23 March 2026)

¹⁰ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/> (accessed: 23 March 2026); for project outputs, see the Zenodo-Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/eosceden/> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

be applied to the value research data might have for other scientific purposes and research questions beyond the original purpose in a research project within which it was created.

In the case of research data and ESS data especially, a clear distinction between primary and secondary value is sometimes less straightforward. E.g., Earth observation data might be collected for the purpose of extending the data base for future research without one specific research question in mind. Furthermore, appraisal responsibilities and procedures between the data producers and the designated curation institution in the long term (e.g., TDR) are often less clear for research data, requiring a more collaborative approach to appraisal (see sec. 6).

3.2 Informational and Evidential Value

The secondary value of data can further be differentiated into two categories: informational and evidential value. The two types of value are not mutually exclusive; data might contain informational and evidential value alike.

In archival appraisal, informational value refers to the lasting value the content of data might have, independent of their original context, providing information on places, people, events, etc. For research data in ESS, this might apply to the information contained e.g., in data from Earth observations and measurements, providing valuable information for future research.

Evidential value on the other hand refers to the data's capacity to give insight into e.g., activities, functions, processes, or practices of the context and framework within which the data was created. While for historical research or the history of science the importance of evidential value is straightforward, for ESS it might be less obvious but also highly relevant to consider. Data might contain important contextual evidence on research processes, methods, experimental or measurement setups, workflows, or scientific practices of lasting value.

3.3 Retrospective and Prospective Appraisal

Archival practice distinguishes between two different approaches regarding the point in time when an appraisal process should take place. Retrospective appraisal is being conducted after the data is no longer needed for the primary purpose it was originally created. Traditionally, appraisal processes have mostly been conducted retrospectively, upon the data's transfer to an archival institution. Prospective appraisal on the other hand aims to appraise the lasting value before the data's creation or during its active usage within its original context. With the digital transformation and the challenges of digital long-term preservation in mind, requiring more extensive documentation on a technical and contextual level, prospective appraisal has become more common in archival practices.

For research data, prospective appraisal has several advantages. It gives the opportunity for a closer interaction with the data producer, allowing for a better understanding and assessment of the data's context and thus its lasting value. Embedding appraisal considerations into research planning (e.g., within data management plans) also enables clearer and earlier decisions about what data will be preserved, thus allowing for a more targeted resource allocation for data preparation and processing during the original research project as well as to align research practices with preservation objectives (see also sec. 6). Retrospective appraisal for research data remains relevant, particularly for legacy data or where no systematic data management was in place.

4 Possible Outcomes of Appraisal

The appraisal process of determining the lasting value of research data should result in a clear course of action regarding the question whether to preserve it in the long term. This can also have implications on other aspects of RDM throughout the active phase of a research project, such as allocation of resources e.g., for creating documentation and metadata, or contacting and negotiating submission agreements for the research data of lasting value with a designated curation institution (e.g., TDR). Thus, for an efficient RDM it is recommended to raise the question of appraising the lasting value of research data as soon as possible within a research project or mission and adapt the appraisal result, if necessary due to developments, etc. over time.

The following paragraphs will shortly outline possible outcomes of an appraisal process for determining the lasting value of research data:

- **Data is no longer needed and has no lasting value:** If the appraisal process determines that the research data is no longer required for the active phase of a research project or other purposes and has no lasting value, the appropriate course of action should be the disposal of the data. Proper documentation of the appraisal decision and reasoning to dispose of the data is essential for accountability and comprehensibility. Disposal of data, when conducted as a result of an appraisal process, is a legitimate and necessary component of responsible and sustainable RDM.
- **Data is required for certain period of time but has no lasting value:** Research data that has been determined not having a lasting value can still be needed to be retained for a specific period of time. This can be the case during the active phase of a research project, for the purpose of validation of research results and publications, or due to required compliance with the policies by e.g., the funders or institutions of the research project. In these cases, the specific retention periods should be defined, adequate storage of the data secured for the defined retention timeframe, and the disposal planned at the end of the retention period.
- **The lasting value of the data is unclear:** The outcome of an appraisal process might also be that the lasting value of the research data cannot be determined at the current point in time. Reasons for that might be e.g., pending analysis of the data within ongoing research projects, emerging methodologies, or novel data types with uncertain significance. In such cases, the data should be retained in a way allowing for its long-term preservation in the future and a point in time in the future scheduled for reappraisal of its lasting value.
- **Data is deemed of lasting value:** Research data that has been determined during the appraisal process to be of lasting value should be preserved in a way that secures its authenticity, integrity, access, and interpretability in the long term throughout

cultural and technological changes. This can be successfully achieved only within a designated curation institution, for research data typically within a TDR or institutional digital archive. It is recommended to choose a suitable designated curation institution, negotiate submission agreements, and prepare the research data according to the designated curation institution's requirements as early as possible, even if the data is being transferred later. Another question to be considered for data that has been deemed of lasting value is, whether it needs to be preserved in its entirety. In some circumstances, the preservation of a representative sample from a large database might be sufficient.

5 Appraisal Criteria for ESS Data

Appraisal criteria provide a structured framework for assessing whether research data should be selected for long-term preservation. In digital preservation practice more broadly, such criteria translate abstract notions of lasting value into transparent and reproducible decision-making processes. Clearly defined criteria support consistency within and across institutions, enable accountability, and facilitate communication between data producers and designated curation institutions.¹¹

While general appraisal principles are widely applicable across disciplines, their operationalization must reflect disciplinary characteristics, data types, and research practices. In ESS, data is often observational, model-based, large-scale, and closely linked to dynamic environmental processes. These characteristics require a careful interpretation of general appraisal criteria in light of domain-specific scientific, technical, and societal contexts. The following sections outline core appraisal criteria and contextualize their particular relevance for ESS data.

5.1 Scientific Relevance and Quality

Scientific relevance and quality constitute fundamental appraisal criteria across disciplines. Data considered for long-term preservation should demonstrate a clear contribution to knowledge production, methodological rigor, and sufficient reliability. Indicators include transparent documentation of methods, evidence of quality control, and reproducibility of results. Retaining scientifically robust data supports the integrity of the scholarly record and enables future verification, reinterpretation, and methodological development. In contrast, insufficiently documented or methodologically weak data may impose preservation burdens without proportional benefit.

ESS data proposed for long-term preservation must demonstrate high scientific value and reliability. Data that underpins critical research questions or have been rigorously quality-controlled are strong candidates. For example, the Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment (GOME) satellite record was appraised as “very important for the scientific community” due to its role in ozone depletion and climate change studies¹². Designated curation institutions often enforce quality standards as part of appraisal—both PANGAEA and the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) apply multi-level quality assessments to ensure submitted data and metadata are consistent and of high quality¹³. Conversely, a poorly documented or error-prone dataset

¹¹ (Whyte & Wilson, 2010); (Gastl-Hartmann, 2022); (Beagrie, 2019)

¹² (Albani & Giaretta, 2009)

¹³ https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Data_policy (accessed: 23 March 2026); https://www.wdc-climate.de/docs/WDCC_quality_assurance.pdf (accessed: 23 March 2026)

may be rejected or require improvement before acceptance for long-term preservation, illustrating that only data meeting state-of-the-art scientific quality and relevance are selected.

5.2 Potential for Reuse

Potential for reuse is a central consideration in the appraisal process for determining the lasting value of research data. Data that can support new research questions, interdisciplinary applications, or methodological reanalysis typically justify preservation and continued stewardship. Reuse potential enhances the long-term return on investment in data production and aligns with open science and FAIR principles¹⁴. Appraisal therefore extends beyond the original research purpose and considers whether data may gain relevance in future scientific, technological, or societal contexts.

In ESS, reuse of data often extends beyond a single disciplinary and spatial context. The greater the likelihood other researchers will reanalyze or repurpose data, the stronger the case for preserving it. Preserving data according to open science and FAIR principles enables new potentials for scientific reanalysis and reuse for new research questions of existing data, thus also reducing the production of redundant research data. For instance, making the Landsat satellite imagery archive openly available in 2008 led to a sharp increase of reuse, downloads, and scientific publications using Landsat data once the data were openly available¹⁵. This case shows how widely Earth observation data can be reused for applications ranging from climate modeling to urban planning, justifying its long-term preservation. Likewise, a hydrological time-series initially collected for a local study might later be reused for continental-scale water resource models. These examples illustrate the necessity to consider interdisciplinary reuse potential in an appraisal process.

5.3 Uniqueness

Uniqueness is a core appraisal criterion for long-term preservation. Data that cannot reasonably be replicated or reconstructed warrant heightened priority. Irreplaceability may result from temporal singularity, spatial specificity, or the practical infeasibility of repeating e.g., measurements, experiments, or simulations. The loss of such data would create irreversible gaps in the evidential and informational record. Appraisal must therefore assess whether equivalent data could be generated again under comparable conditions.

¹⁴ (Wilkinson, et al., 2016); <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

¹⁵ <https://landsat.gsfc.nasa.gov/article/fifteen-years-of-open-data-allows-advancements-in-landsat-use-and-research/> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

Many observations in ESS document transient environmental states or long-term change processes. According to the review criteria of the journal *Earth System Science Data*, any observations that cannot be easily replicated—e.g., one-time experiments or measurements of Earth system changes—are inherently valuable¹⁶. A prime example is the ESA GOME satellite ozone dataset, which “is unique because it provides more than 14 years [of] global coverage”¹⁷. Such a long, uninterrupted record of a critical variable is impossible to recollect once the satellite mission ends, underscoring its uniqueness. Similarly, data from a rare field campaign (e.g., measurements during a volcanic eruption or an ocean drilling program) would be considered unique and chosen for long-term preservation because future opportunities to gather the same information are limited or non-existent.

5.4 Compliance with Legal, Ethical, and Funding Requirements

Compliance with legal, ethical, and policy frameworks is a prerequisite for long-term preservation. Designated curation institutions must ensure that preservation does not violate intellectual property rights, data protection regulations, contractual agreements, or other regulatory obligations. Appraisal therefore includes assessing rights status, licensing conditions, consent frameworks, and funder mandates. At the same time, regulatory and policy requirements increasingly function as drivers for preservation, particularly where legislation or funding conditions mandate long-term availability of research data.

In Germany, an ESS specific policy—the Geological Data Act (GeoldG)—makes reporting and preserving certain geoscientific data mandatory by law¹⁸. Such data would be appraised favourably since long-term preservation is a legal requirement. Funding agencies and journals also increasingly play a driving force in advancing the preservation of research data. The German Research Foundation (DFG) and the EU Research and Innovation programmes generally encourage and partially require the openness and preservation of data as part of their open-science requirements. On the other hand, designated curation institutions must respect restrictions. PANGAEA notes that in accordance with legal requirements such as copyright and data protection laws (GDPR), they will permanently remove published data if a legitimate deletion request arises, replacing it with a tombstone notice in the DOI landing page¹⁹. This example shows the relevance of weighing ethical and legal compliance during an appraisal process. Data containing sensitive information, e.g., personal data, endangered species locations, or classified content might be rejected or require appropriate access

¹⁶ https://www.earth-system-science-data.net/peer_review/review_criteria.html (accessed: 23 March 2026)

¹⁷ (Albani & Giaretta, 2009)

¹⁸ <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/geoldg/> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

¹⁹ <https://www.pangaea.de/about/preservation.php> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

restriction. Ultimately, only data that can be preserved in line with all legal, ethical, and funding requirements is selected for long-term preservation.

5.5 Historical and Cultural Significance

Research data may hold value beyond immediate scientific utility. Archival theory recognizes that data documenting significant developments or transformative events can acquire importance over time. Such relevance often becomes fully visible only retrospectively. Appraisal therefore considers whether data represents milestones, baseline measurements, or historically situated observations that contribute to the continuity of the scientific record.

ESS data with historical or cultural importance merit preservation even if their immediate scientific use is limited. Such data forms the scientific heritage and provide baselines for change. A classic example is the Mauna Loa CO₂ record—the longest-running direct measurement of atmospheric CO₂ (started in 1958)²⁰. This iconic time-series is preserved because of its pivotal role in documenting climate change history. Similarly, early remote sensing images (e.g., the first Landsat 1 satellite images from 1972) and historical maps or survey records are kept as they capture past Earth conditions that future generations can study. Preserving these records has cultural significance: for instance, digitized 19th-century ship logbooks of weather observations not only extend climate databases but also provide evidence of early scientific expeditions. Designated curation institutions will appraise datasets for such significance—data associated with notable events (e.g., a major drought, a famous eruption) or that represent first-of-its-kind observations often get selected to ensure the continuity of the scientific record.

5.6 Formal and Technical Adequacy

Formal and technical adequacy are operational prerequisites for sustainable long-term preservation. Data must be technically processable, sufficiently documented, and stored in sustainable, community-standard file formats to remain accessible and interpretable over time.²¹ Appraisal therefore evaluates whether data can be preserved using available infrastructure and expertise, including assessment of file formats, metadata completeness, and documentation quality.

For long-term preservation, data must be in a technically sound state. Appraisal looks at whether the data is well structured, documented, and stored in sustainable file formats.

²⁰ <https://gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends/> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

²¹ For more detailed guidelines on the topic of preparation of data for long-term preservation, see: (Valena & Schürmann, 2024)

Designated curation institutions may reject or require reformatting of data that is technically inadequate. For example, PANGAEA generally does not accept raw instrument data alone unless a complementary variant in a higher processing level is provided, and any accepted raw data are clearly marked with low processing level and come with no usability guarantees²². This policy illustrates that data needs to be processed and described sufficiently (e.g., with metadata, calibration information, etc.) to be fit for long-term preservation. Likewise, the WDCC only accepts data in sustainable, open, and community-standard file formats, preferably in NetCDF/CF²³. Ensuring technical adequacy secures the data can be accessed and interpreted in the future. E.g., a geochemical dataset in an obscure proprietary file format or lacking sufficient metadata and documentation would be flagged during appraisal and possibly not preserved until corrected. In summary, only data that meets formal criteria (proper formats, complete metadata and documentation, valid file integrity) are accepted for long-term preservation.

²² <https://www.pangaea.de/about/preservation.php> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

²³ https://www.wdc-climate.de/docs/WDCC_User_Guide.pdf (accessed: 23 March 2026)

6 Considerations for an Appraisal Process in ESS

In ESS, one of the major challenges for appraisal procedures is the process of selecting the data of lasting value from a diverse and complex range of data output, ranging from raw unprocessed instrument data, data and data products of various processing levels²⁴ and resolution, derived and accumulated data, to modeling and simulation data output. This chapter will highlight relevant stakeholders in ESS and their role within an appraisal process throughout the data life cycle and outline practical suggestions for a collaborative approach to appraisal in ESS.

6.1 Stakeholders and their Role in an Appraisal Process

Responsibilities and procedures for an appraisal process are in traditional archival practices typically clearly defined and assigned, in the case of governmental institutions, even legally mandated. Once the data is no longer needed for its primary purpose and the designated retention period has expired, the data is in its entirety offered to the responsible archive as the designated curation institution in the long term. Here a trained archivist conducts the appraisal process, determining which data is of lasting value and which data is being disposed of.

In science, the situation is somewhat more complex. Responsibilities and procedures for an appraisal process, especially in the case of research data, are less clearly defined. Several stakeholders play an important role throughout the data life cycle in the actual process of determining which data is being preserved, requiring a more collaborative approach to appraisal.²⁵ The DCC Curation Lifecycle Model below (see Fig. 1) illustrates the importance of appraisal within the data life cycle and can be adapted to define specific roles and responsibilities.

6.1.1 Data Producers

Potentially highly relevant data for ESS is being produced and collected by a wide range of stakeholders. Among these data producers are e.g., individual scientists, temporary research projects or missions, or institutions committed to gathering long-term monitoring data from remote sensing or in-situ observations, such as research institutes, regional, national, and international agencies, but also commercial and military stakeholders.

²⁴ <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn/earth-observation-data-basics/data-processing-levels> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

²⁵ (Dorey, Hurley, & Knazook, 2022); (Whyte & Wilson, 2010)

²⁶ (Higgins, 2008)

Figure 1: DCC Curation Lifecycle Model²⁶

Data producers as the initial custodians and curators of the produced data play an important role within the appraisal process. They inevitably undertake a form of preselection when deciding which of the produced data and in which variation is being offered to a designated curation institution for its long-term preservation. This preselection constitutes already an initial appraisal decision, whether it is being consciously recognized as such or not, shaping the collection of data that even becomes eligible for long-term preservation. Being aware of this role and responsibility as data producers within an appraisal framework is crucial and should be approached based on clearly defined criteria for evaluating the data's lasting value.

6.1.2 Designated Curation Institution in the Long Term

Digital long-term preservation is based on the ability to preserve data in a way that secures its authenticity, integrity, access, and interpretability throughout cultural and technological changes. This can be successfully accomplished only within a designated curation institution willing and capable to take over responsibility for the data in the long term and to conduct preservation actions and curation over time. In the case of research data, this role of designated curation institutions is typically assumed by subject-specific or institutional trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs).²⁷

Consequently, the designated curation institutions play a crucial role within an appraisal framework for ESS data, by deciding which data they accept into their digital archive, thus effectively securing its long-term preservation. Based on their mission and mandate as well as preservation approach, designated curation institutions typically have preservation and collection policies in place, outlining requirements and criteria for the data's acceptance into their collection. Technical requirements (e.g., on metadata, documentation, or file formats) function not only as quality assurance but can also have an impact on the eligibility of certain types of data for acceptance and submission into a specific designated curation institution, e.g., regarding their levels of processing. More impactful from an appraisal perspective is the disciplinary or thematic scope as well as defined criteria for assessing the data's lasting value, ideally defined within the collection policy of the designated curation institution. Such a collection policy offers guidance for data producers, increases transparency on appraisal practices, as well as provides a basis for structured and consistent appraisal decisions. Having an established appraisal process with clearly defined criteria is also a requirement in all major certification and audit frameworks for trustworthy repositories.²⁸

²⁷ (Andreu, et al., 2023); (L'Hours, et al., 2022); (Schürmann & Valena, 2026)

²⁸ Particularly CoreTrustSeal, DIN 31644 (nestor Seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives), and ISO 16363 (Audit and Certification of Trustworthy Digital Repositories). See: (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2025); (nestor-Arbeitsgruppe Zertifizierung, 2024); (The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, 2024)

6.1.3 Discipline-Specific Stakeholders

ESS is comprised of a variety of different disciplines, each of which might have specific needs and requirements regarding the question which data and in what form to preserve in the long term for their scientific practices. Both data producers and designated curation institutions operate within the framework of their respective disciplines. Thus, incorporating input from the scientific communities and the specific disciplines into the appraisal process, including the perspective of current and future data users, is essential.

These discipline-specific stakeholders may include e.g., expert associations, standardization bodies, research institutes, advisory boards, research funders, or national and international agencies. Their role is to offer overarching guidance and orientation in the appraisal process by articulating more detailed and elaborate criteria for assessing the lasting value of data, data types, or data products within their field. This can apply either broadly to a discipline or specifically to researchers or research projects and missions under their institutional umbrella. By offering overarching guidance, discipline-specific stakeholders support the other actors in making informed appraisal decisions and ensure that these decisions are aligned with broader scientific priorities and community needs.

6.2 Suggestions for a Cooperative Approach to Appraisal of ESS Data

Appraisal as a structured, systematic, transparent, and documented process is essential for identifying all relevant and important data of lasting value within ESS and securing its long-term preservation. Considering the different stakeholders and their role, it becomes evident that a cooperative approach to appraisal is most feasible and highly advisable, utilizing the expertise of data producers and designated curation institutions alike as well as taking discipline-specific guidance into account. The following paragraphs outline some suggestions for a cooperative approach to the appraisal of ESS data.

6.2.1 Prospective Appraisal in ESS

In ESS, considerable attention is typically given to defining what data is collected and for which scientific purpose. Measurement strategies, sensor configurations, sampling intervals, and model scenarios are often carefully designed before data acquisition begins. This prospective planning provides an opportunity to assess the data's lasting value before it is generated or while still in active use within research projects.

It is recommended to address appraisal of the data's lasting value based on clearly formulated criteria (see sec. 5) as early as possible, ideally already during the planning phase of a research project or mission. This not only increases the awareness for the data's potential relevance

beyond the project's purpose, but also helps to allocate the often limited resources for preservation efforts (e.g., creating documentation and metadata) on data types and data variations most critical to preserve for the long term.

6.2.2 Utilization of Data Management Plans (DMPs)

A useful framework to approach and document appraisal considerations within research projects and missions is the data management plan (DMP). Including appraisal decisions and its reasoning in the DMP supports a structured and systematic approach to appraisal within research projects and missions.²⁹ At the same time, it improves data management in general by determining the lifespan, assigning specific retention periods, or allowing for controlled deletion of certain data where accordingly indicated by the outcome of the appraisal considerations. Thus, it is advisable to explicitly address appraisal in the DMP. Ongoing actualization of the DMP ensures that appraisal decisions adapt if required by evolving research realities throughout the project's lifespan.

6.2.3 Coordination between Data Producers and Designated Curation Institutions

A coordination between data producers and designated curation institutions as early as possible is highly recommended for several reasons. Technical specifications and requirements (e.g., accepted file formats, structure of the data, levels of documentation and metadata) vary depending on the implemented preservation strategies within a specific curation institution. Considering these already during the phase of data collection and data preparation will reduce the risk of time consuming reformatting later on. Furthermore, an early collaborative initial appraisal will ensure an alignment in appraisal criteria for assessing the data's lasting value as well as make sure the data fits with the collection policy and scope of the designated curation institution. Such proactive communication facilitates smoother ingestion processes and ensures that appraisal decisions are aligned with long-term preservation capabilities and policies.

²⁹ (Beagrie, 2019); (Gastl-Hartmann, 2022)

7 Outlook

Having well-established and standardized appraisal practices for the long-term preservation of research data within RDM is a crucial aspect for a sustainable data culture in ESS. Looking ahead, the output of currently ongoing projects on the appraisal of research data should be closely monitored, particularly the nestor working group “Prozesse und Kriterien zur Bewertung von Forschungsdaten”³⁰ [Processes and criteria for the appraisal of research data] on a National level as well as the project “EOSC EDEN Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level”³¹ on a European level. The results, output, and developed standards from these projects, expected to be available within this and next year, should serve as a basis for the development of more detailed discipline and/or data-type specific recommendations and standards for appraisal procedures and practices of ESS data for long-term preservation.

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³⁰ https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/DE/Arbeitsgruppen/AG_Archivstandard/ag_archivstandard_node.html (accessed: 23 March 2026)

³¹ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/> (accessed: 23 March 2026); for project outputs, see the Zenodo-Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/eosceden/> (accessed: 23 March 2026)

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